

“USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN TEACHING EFL CLASSES”

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Abstract: The idea of using authentic material in language teaching is supported among references and many professionals in the field of language pedagogy. Authentic material provides the learners with many significant advantages and promotes them with high motivation and interest in language learning and lead to improving communicative competence (Guariento & Morley, 2001; Wilcox et al., 1999).

Authentic materials are among the most important tools a teacher can and must use in class in order to make his/her teaching go smoothly and be effective in transmitting the necessary knowledge to all students. In this paper, the writers will discuss the Effect of Using Authentic Materials in teaching, because a number of studies point out that the use of authentic materials is regarded a useful means to motivate learners, arouse their interest and expose them to the real language they will face in the real world.

Key Words: Authentic Materials; Advantages and Disadvantages of Authentic Materials; Communicative Approach language learning; EFL; curriculum; educational resources

Introduction

One of the words that has been creeping into English teaching in the past few years is 'authentic'. The term authentic by definition means that done or made in an original way and at the same time authentic materials can be defined in a various ways in different spheres. The term is still being discussed topic among pedagogues and researchers who give variety definitions on which can be named as authentic materials. Since the mid-1970s communicative language teaching has considered a consistent need to develop students' skills for the real world. In today's globalizing era the importance of educational quality that needs to be modernized is more compulsory than ever before. To reach this quality, more effective, creative and valid approaches should be taken. As well as, regarding the language learning classes, authentic atmosphere of target language should be created with the usage of authentic materials. Martinez (2002), defines authentic materials as the materials which are prepared for native speakers and not designed to be used for teaching purposes. Kilickaya (2004) has another definition for authentic materials, which is "exposure to real language and use in its own community." Nowadays, preparing students for real life situations is of

almost concern for English language teachers, especially in EFL classes. Therefore, like other teachers around the world, especially in places where English is a foreign language, teachers need to adopt effective teaching materials, in order to help their students to learn English better, as well as prepare them to communicate with the outside world. Bacon and Fineman (1990: 459), state that teachers need to "find ways and means of exploiting authentic materials in classroom instructions." Many researchers state that if students are willing to use English language sufficiently, they must be exposed to the language, exactly as it is used in real life situations by native speakers. Researchers claim that when authentic materials are used with the purpose of students 'learning, students will have a sense that the real language for communication is being learnt, as opposed to classroom language itself. In contrast to the design of the text books, authentic materials are intrinsically more active, interesting and stimulating (Lee, 1995; Little, Devitt & Singleton, 1988; Peacock, 1997; Shei, 2001).

Definitions of Authentic Materials: The definitions of authentic materials are slightly different in literature. What is common in these definitions is 'exposure to real language and its use in its own community'. Authentic material is any material written in English that was not created for intentional use in the English language classroom. Using this content to teach the English language can make the learning process even more engaging, imaginative and motivating for students. It can also be useful to elicit genuine responses from learners. Rogers (1988) defines it as 'appropriate' and 'quality' in terms of goals, objectives, learner needs and interest and 'natural' in terms of real life and meaningful communication (p. 467). Jordan (1997, p. 113) refers to authentic texts as texts that are not written for language teaching purposes. Authentic materials is significant since it increases students' motivation for learning, makes the learner be exposed to the 'real' language as discussed by Guariento & Morley (2001, p. 347).

Sources: There are lots of resources available to English language teachers today: from textbooks to online teaching tools, they can all aid and enrich English lessons. Many teachers also introduce authentic English material into their lessons to expose learners to the language as it is spoken in the real world. When people first think of authentic materials, they usually assume that we are talking about newspaper and magazine articles. However, the term can also encompass such things as songs, web pages, radio & TV broadcasts, films, leaflets, flyers, posters, indeed anything written in the target language and used unedited in the classroom.

The materials used, will of course, depend on the 'usual' factors:

topic

target language area

skills

students' needs and interests

It's no good trying to get your students fascinated by a text on the latest art movie if they are all fans of action films. You might as well save your time and energy and just use the text book!

The use of Authentic Materials: The great thing about using authentic material is that it is everywhere, which makes it easy to find, and simple for learners to practice English in their own time. Remember that it isn't limited to articles from newspapers and magazines. Songs, TV programs and films, radio and podcasts, leaflets, menus – anything written in English constitutes authentic material.

Selecting authentic material

The best content to select depends on the learners, their level of English and the course content the teacher wishes to focus on. It's also a good idea to find out the learners' interests – after all, there's no point trying to get students fascinated by a text on the latest sci-fi movie if they're all fans of action films.

The materials should reflect a situation that learners may face in an English-speaking environment – this will help them transition into a world where English is the norm. In this world, people use abbreviations, body language is important and they'll use “filler” sounds – such as “ump” – when they are speaking English – and learners will encounter these in authentic material.

It's important not to overwhelm learners with the first piece of authentic material. So, to begin with, choose articles, songs or sections of TV programs or movies which aren't too difficult to understand or take too long to get through. Unlike traditional materials that have been created especially for second language learners, they aren't structured in a special way and they don't use specific grammar or vocabulary because they assume that the reader can understand the language used to a native level.

Using authentic materials brings:

1. Creativity to the classroom

As we mentioned earlier, they allow language teachers to become more creative in the materials they use in the classroom, bring the language to life and inspire and motivate their students.

“Interest is a powerful motivational process that energizes learning, guides academic and career trajectories, and is essential to academic success...” said Professor of Psychology, Judith Harackiewicz and colleagues in their aptly named 2016 paper ‘Interest Matters: The Importance ...’ *“Promoting interest can contribute to a m of Promoting Interest in Education ‘ore engaged, motivated, learning experience for students.”*

2. Help the student develop a relationship with the language

Using these real-life language materials can also help your ESL student to form a meaningful connection with the language and relate better to the content, supporting the entire learning experience.

3. Expose the student to real-world English usage

Of course, we’re not just teaching students English as an academic pursuit. We want them to be able to use the language in the real world to achieve their goals, progress in their careers, move to an English-speaking country and succeed in whatever they set their minds to.

As linguist Christine Nuttall Heinemann said in her 1996 book, ‘Teaching Reading Skills in a Foreign Language’; *“authentic texts can be motivating because they are proof that the language is used for real-life purposes by real people”*.

Without exposure to these kinds of authentic language materials, they may struggle to cope when using the language outside of the classroom.

Some ways to use authentic material:

Here are two ideas for using authentic material in class: do remember to develop the ideas into proper lesson plans and explain the aims thoroughly to your learners...

1. Restaurant menus: order your favorite dish

Food is important to everyone, so introduce language learners to some of the common dishes in English-speaking countries so that they will be able to order meals with confidence. Many restaurants have their menus online, so you can easily download them (no need to walk or drive around the neighborhood!). Try to use local restaurants, which will make it more meaningful for your students, and make sure you have plenty of copies of the menu.

You can then either go through the menu and ask students to guess what the meals are, or they can write down what they would order. You could use different menus for each course, which would widen the types of dishes you can cover during the learning activity. You or another team member could pretend to be the waiter or waitress and your students can practice their spoken English by reading their order back to you.

At the end of the task, you could encourage learners to add up the cost of their courses to calculate their bill – and even ask them to add on a 10% tip to mirror the experience of being in a real restaurant.

Remember, that these suggestions focus on different skills, so you could use them to form lesson plans for a “speaking” lesson, a “reading” lesson, etc.

2. Songs: recognizing English lyrics

Listening to songs with English lyrics is a great way of boosting skills in listening and pronunciation, and confidence in using the language. And students will always respond positively to a lesson that involves their favorite singer or bands. Ask your learners to write down their favorite artist and a song by them that they like and have listened to a few times. They can then try to remember the lyrics, or look at the video on YouTube – they only need to write down a few lines of the song.

Then ask them to really listen to the lyrics for useful vocabulary, phrases and expressions for everyday language that includes colloquial speech. The language used in lyrics can be casual, tell a simple story or convey strong emotions, which should help learners to establish a connection with the language because it will give them new ways to describe their feelings in different situations. You could even ask them to come up with alternative words, as a way of further increasing and using their vocabulary.

Some song lyrics are commonly misheard, so you could create a quiz in which learners have to choose the next words – words that grammatically fit into the lyrics. This can be a funny lesson – for you as well as your students!

We’d love to hear from you if you have used authentic material in the classroom – or are using authentic material to learn English. Authentic materials are audio, print and video materials that have not been designed for deliberate use in the English language classroom.

Authentic materials may fall into two main categories - print and auditory.

Let’s check out some examples of authentic materials from each category:

AUTHENTIC PRINT MATERIALS	AUTHENTIC AUDITORY MATERIALS
Job applications	TV commercials
Restaurant menus	Radio broadcasts
Food labels	Movies
TV guides	Podcasts
Magazines	E-books
Newspapers	Songs
Journal articles	
Blog posts	
Novels	
Leaflets	

Advantages and Disadvantages of using authentic materials:

The main advantages of using authentic materials are (Philips and Shuttlesworth 1978; Clarke 1989; Peacock 1997, cited in Richards, 2001):

They have a positive effect on learner motivation. They provide authentic cultural information. They provide exposure to real language. They relate more closely to learners' needs. They support a more creative approach to teaching. We can claim that learners are being exposed to real language and they feel that they are learning the 'real' language. These are what make us excited and willing to use authentic materials in our classrooms, but while using them, it is inevitable that we face some problems.

Disadvantages of Using Authentic Materials

Richards (2001, p. 253) points out that alongside with these advantages, authentic materials often contain difficult language, unneeded vocabulary items and complex language structures, which causes a burden for the teacher in lower-level classes. Martinez (2002) mentions that authentic materials may be too culturally biased and too many structures are mixed, causing lower levels have a hard time decoding the texts. There comes the question of when authentic materials should be introduced and used in a classroom; in other words, can we use authentic materials regardless of our students' level?

Using Authentic Materials: At Which Level?

Guariento & Morley (2001) claim that at post-intermediate level, the use of authentic materials is available for use in classroom. This might be attributed to the fact that at this level, most students master a wide range of vocabulary in the target language and all of the structures. They also note that at lower levels, the use of authentic materials may cause students to feel de-motivated and frustrated since they lack many lexical items and structures used in the target language. Matsuata (n.d.) states that the use of authentic materials is a burden for the instructors teaching beginning students as they have to spend a lot of time to prepare for authentic materials regarding the ability level of the students.

Do all these mean we are not able to use authentic materials in lower-level classes apart from post-intermediate and advanced levels? According to the findings of the survey carried out by Chavez (1998), learners enjoy dealing with authentic materials since they enable them to interact with the real language and its use. Also, they do not consider authentic situations or materials innately difficult. However, learners state that they need pedagogical support especially in listening situations and when reading literary texts such as the provision of a full range of cues (auditory and visual including written language).

What Can be Done to Overcome Difficulties We Face?

We may conclude that learners feel better with authentic materials helping them involve in the 'real' language as long as we, as teachers, provide them with pedagogical support. In order to achieve this, we have a wide range of choices.

Martinez (2002) suggests that teachers may use authentic materials for the learners to listen for the gist of the information presented and also he adds that by using authentic materials teachers will have the opportunity to encourage students to read for pleasure especially certain topics of their interest. Matsuta (n.d.) claims that using audio-visual materials aiding students' comprehension is beneficial since it will prevent students especially beginning ones from being frustrated about authentic materials. Materials such as popular and traditional songs will help us to create a non-threatening environment.

Guariento & Moley (2001) suggest that authentic materials should be used in accordance with students' ability and adds that suitable tasks can be given to learners in which total understanding is not important. According to Jordan (1997), in the earlier stages, non-authentic materials can be used, but stresses that upon students' dealing with materials from their own subject area, authentic materials should be introduced.

Conclusion

Authentic materials enable learners to interact with the real language and content rather than the form. Learners feel that they are learning a target language as it is used outside the classroom. Considering this, it may not be wrong to say that at any level authentic materials should be used to complete the gap between the competency and performance of the language learners, which is a common problem among the nonnative speakers. This requires the language patterns being put into practice in real life situations. Since learning about a culture is not accepting it and the role of the culture in the materials is just to create learner interest towards the target language, there should be a variety of culture in the materials, not a specific one.

As can be seen, using authentic materials is a relatively easy and convenient way of improving not only your students' general skills, but also their confidence in a real situation. This is only a brief introduction to the ideas involved, but some of these ideas could easily be expanded to form part of a motivating and effective course.

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